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Monthly Report February 2026

SENTINEL Wild Birds

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SUMMARY REPORT

1. OVERVIEW

SENTINEL Wild Birds aims to enhance the understanding of highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) virus dynamics in wild bird populations by conducting active surveillance at key locations in and near Europe. These locations are divided into the following surveillance nodes: Node 1 Gulf of Finland (Finland, Estonia), Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea (Sweden, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland), Node 3 Western Black Sea (Ukraine), Node 4 Eastern Black Sea (Georgia), Node 5 Wadden Sea (the Netherlands), Node 6 Lake Constance (Germany, Austria, Switzerland), Node 7 Veneto Region (Italy), Node 8 Camargue (France), and Node 9 Gulf of Cadiz (Spain). This monthly summary provides an update on sampled wild birds as part of an early warning system to support wildlife management and disease prevention efforts. The data in this report are based on previously unpublished samples from six nodes, collected from November 2025 to February 2026.

Note that the numbers presented in this and previous monthly reports are based on data extracts prepared at the time of analysis. As some samples may be re-analysed or reported in more than one period, the numbers reported across different monthly summaries are not strictly additive and may differ slightly from aggregated totals in the underlying dataset.

2. RESULTS

2.1 DATA COLLECTION

Since the last monthly report was published on 27th of January 2026 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18391271>), and as of 15th February 2026, test results have been submitted for 2,347 samples taken from 1,332 individuals representing 32 taxa from six nodes in and near Europe (Table 1). Of the 2,347 collected samples, 840 (36%) were tracheal/oropharyngeal swabs, 840 (36%) cloacal swabs, 293 (12%) fecal samples, 173 (7%) feather swabs, 166 (7%) combined swabs (choana + cloacal), 16 (<1%) choana swabs, 16 (<1%) pooled organs, 2 (<1%) water samples, and 1 (<1%) brain samples.

Prevalence and host species sampled

The most sampled species were Mallard (620 individuals) and Eurasian Teal (206 individuals; Table 1). Highest bird-level prevalence in species with a sample size of at least 50 individuals was found in Greylag Goose (4%; n=52), Mallard (4%, n=620), Black-headed Gull (3%, n=61), Eurasian Wigeon (3%, n=67), and Eurasian Teal (2%, n=206). Overall bird-level prevalence was 3% (35 of 1,332 individuals; Table 1).

TABLE 1 Most recently sampled individuals in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Total number of individuals sampled in the wild, number of individuals tested positive for avian influenza virus as well as bird-level prevalence. The table includes previously unpublished samples from November 2025 to February 2026.

Group/species	Node 3 Ukraine		Node 4 Georgia		Node 6 Austria		Node 6 Germany		Node 6 Switzerland		Node 7 Italy		Node 8 France		Node 9 Spain		Total		
	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Prev.
<i>Waterfowl</i>																			
Mute Swan	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
Whooper Swan	0	0	0	0	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	20	0	0%
Greylag Goose	0	0	0	0	51	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	52	2	4%
Shelduck	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	7	0	0%
Ruddy Shelduck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
Egyptian Goose	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0%
Anas sp.	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0%
Mallard	113	16	457	5	19	1	1	0	15	0	12	0	3	0	0	0	620	22	4%
Domestic Mallard	0	0	24	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24	0	0%
Gadwall	0	0	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	1	33%
Northern Pintail	2	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	14	0	0%
Eurasian Wigeon	1	0	1	0	62	2	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	67	2	3%
Eurasian Teal	2	0	26	0	12	0	0	0	3	0	151	3	12	1	0	0	206	4	2%
Common Pochard	0	0	9	1	6	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16	2	13%
Greater Scaup	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0%
Tufted Duck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0%
Common Merganser	0	0	0	0	67	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	67	0	0%
<i>Grebes</i>																			
Black-necked Grebe	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0%
Great Crested Grebe	0	0	1	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0%
<i>Cormorants</i>																			
Great Cormorant	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	43	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	44	0	0%
<i>Herons, storks</i>																			
Grey Heron	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
White Stork	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0%
<i>Rails</i>																			
Eurasian Coot	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	7	0	0%
<i>Waders</i>																			
Dunlin	49	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	49	0	0%
Numenius sp.	0	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	0	0%
<i>Larids</i>																			
Larus sp.	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0%
Black-headed Gull	0	0	3	0	33	0	22	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	61	2	3%
Black-legged Kittiwake	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0%
European Herring Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
Mediterranean Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0%
Lesser Black-backed Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	8	0	0%
<i>Others</i>																			
Water sample	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18	0	18	0	0%
Total	168	16	537	7	297	6	34	2	76	0	177	3	15	1	28	0	1332	35	3%

HPAI detection

Of all samples, 40 (2%) tested positive for avian influenza virus, of which 1 (<0.1%) sample was positive for highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI; H5) virus (Figure 1; Table 2). This HPAI virus-positive sample originated from a full grown female Eurasian Teal in France, sampled in January 2026.

Other subtypes

Subtyped rRT-PCR-positive samples included three H5 viruses with undetermined NA subtypes (one male and two female Mallards from Ukraine), one H16N3 (female Black-headed Gull from Germany), and one N1 with undetermined HA subtype (male Eurasian Teal from Italy). One female Eurasian Teal from Italy was also determined as H9N2 by Next Generation Sequencing.

FIGURE 1 Sample sites in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Sample sites for the 1,332 individuals sampled in Ukraine, Georgia, Austria, Germany, Switzerland, Italy, France, and Spain. The figure includes previously unpublished samples from November 2025 to February 2026.

A weekly compilation of all 29,935 samples (positive and negative; including previously published), collected at each node from August 2024 to February 2026, can be seen in Figure 2. Proportion of positive individuals (bird-level prevalence) per week over the total project period, all nodes combined, can be seen in Figure 3. During autumn and winter 2025, there are peaks of high bird-level prevalence in August and September followed by a sustained high proportion of positive individuals until beginning of December when the prevalence dropped to a low level which was sustained through January and beginning of February (Figure 3).

TABLE 2 Most recently collected samples in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Total number of collected samples as well as number of samples positive for avian influenza virus. The table includes previously unpublished samples from November 2025 to February 2026.

Group/species	Node 3 Ukraine			Node 4 Georgia			Node 6 Austria			Node 6 Germany			Node 6 Switzerland			Node 7 Italy			Node 8 France			Node 9 Spain			Total					
	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI			
<i>Waterfowl</i>																														
Mute Swan	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Whooper Swan	0	0	0	0	0	0	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	20	0	0
Greylag Goose	0	0	0	0	0	0	51	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	52	2	0
Shelduck	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17	0	0
Ruddy Shelduck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Egyptian Goose	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0
Anas sp.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0
Mallard	226	20	0	836	6	0	19	1	0	1	0	0	15	0	0	36	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1139	27	0
Domestic Mallard	0	0	0	45	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	45	0	0
Gadwall	0	0	0	6	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	1	0
Northern Pintail	4	0	0	18	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	31	0	0
Eurasian Wigeon	2	0	0	2	0	0	62	2	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	69	2	0
Eurasian Teal	4	0	0	52	0	0	12	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	453	3	0	24	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	548	4	1
Common Pochard	0	0	0	18	1	0	6	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25	2	0
Greater Scaup	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Tufted Duck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0
Common Merganser	0	0	0	0	0	0	67	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	67	0	0
<i>Grebes</i>																														
Black-necked Grebe	0	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	0	0
Great Crested Grebe	0	0	0	2	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0
<i>Cormorants</i>																														
Great Cormorant	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	43	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	44	0	0
<i>Hérons, storks</i>																														
Grey Heron	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
White Stork	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0
<i>Rails</i>																														
Eurasian Coot	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	0	0
<i>Waders</i>																														
Dunlin	98	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	98	0	0
Numenius sp.	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	0	0
<i>Larids</i>																														
Larus sp.	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	0
Black-headed Gull	0	0	0	4	0	0	33	0	0	22	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	0	0	61	2	0
Black-legged Kittiwake	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
European Herring Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Mediterranean Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Lesser Black-backed Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16	0	0	16	0	0
<i>Others</i>																														
Water sample	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	36	0	0	0	0	0	36	0	0
Total	336	20	0	990	8	0	297	6	0	34	2	0	76	0	0	528	3	0	30	1	1	56	0	0	2347	40	1			

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FIGURE 2 Weekly summary of collected samples in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. In total, 29,935 samples (negative samples in blue; samples positive for avian influenza virus in orange) have been collected at nine nodes between August 2024 and February 2026, yielding 2,145 samples positive for avian influenza virus, including 91 samples positive for HPAI virus. The figures also include samples published in previous reports.

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Figure 3 Weekly bird-level prevalence of avian influenza virus in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Weekly prevalence of individuals positive for avian influenza virus from all nodes combined between August 2024 and February 2026, separated for each year. The figures only include bird samples (excluding mussels and water samples). The number of individuals (here: any individual bird sampled on a given day) are included at the top of the figure.

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2.2 GENOMICS SUMMARY

Since the last report was published on 27th of January 2026 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18391271>), and as of the 15th of February 2026, 20 new H5 sequences have been generated from samples positive for avian influenza virus, all of which were of the H5N1 subtype. These samples were collected from Mallards in Sweden (Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea; N=9) and the Netherlands (Node 5 Wadden Sea; N=10), as well as a Eurasian Teal in Italy (Node 7 Veneto Region; N=1).

Genetic analysis of the haemagglutinin (HA) gene sequences from these sequences found that all belonged to the H5 clade 2.3.4.4b of highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) (Figure 4A).

The majority (N=10; three from Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea, six from Node 5 Wadden Sea and one from Node 7 Veneto Region) of the H5 HPAI sequences were classified as the DI.2.1 sub-genotype of the EA-2024-DI genotype, according to the European Union Reference Laboratory for Avian Influenza classification system (<https://github.com/izsvenezie-virology/genin2>). However, the other ten H5 HPAI sequences (six from Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea and four from Node 5 Wadden Sea) could not be genotyped due to missing viral genome segments. These sequences were obtained from samples collected on separate occasions across a 38-day period (28th October – 5th December 2025) and found to be similar to other H5N1 DI.2.1 sequences from the SENTINEL Wild Birds project from Latvia, Sweden (both Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea) and France (Node 8 Camargue Region; Figure 4B). Additionally, these DI.2.1 sequences collected within the project show similarity to other sequences of the same H5 genotype collected from across Europe and surrounding countries.

The Nextstrain builds are available on the SENTINEL Wild Birds Group (<https://nextstrain.org/groups/SentinelWildBirds>).

Aside from the H5 sequences, there have been 17 non-H5 avian influenza sequences generated from samples collected in Estonia (Node 1 Gulf of Finland; N=4), Sweden (Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea; N=7), Austria (Node 6 Lake Constance Region; N=3) and Italy (Node 7 Veneto Region; N=3). These samples were collected from Mallards (N=11), Eurasian Teal (N=3), Greylag Goose (N=2) and Eurasian Wigeon (N=1) and were of the following subtypes: 3xH1N1, 1xH2N3, 2xH3N8, 1xH4N6, 2xH9N2, 2xH10N1, 1xH10N2, 2xH11N9, 1xH12N2, 1xH6Nx, and 1xHxN4.

This analysis is based on data obtained from the GISAID EpiFlu platform (Elbe and Buckland-Merrett 2017; Shu and McCauley 2017) up to 16th February 2026, and is accessible at <https://doi.org/10.55876/gis8.260218pd>. Where sequences were included that are under a publishing embargo at the time of writing, specific permission to utilise these data was obtained from the Data Provider.

A

B

FIGURE 4 Phylogenetic analyses of the H5 HA sequences generated by Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea, Node 5 Wadden Sea and Node 7 Veneto Region. A. Image of the H5 HA sequences generated by the SENTINEL Wild Birds project, with the 2.3.4.4b and EA-nonGsGd clades highlighted. **B.** Zoom image of the HA tree focusing on the H5 highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) clade 2.3.4.4b sequences from Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea, Node 5 Wadden Sea, Node 7 Veneto Region, and Node 8 Camargue Region in relation to other sequences from Europe and surrounding countries. The sequences from the SENTINEL Wild Birds project submitted during this reporting period are annotated with an asterisk (*). In **A** and **B** tip shapes are coloured according to the sampling node.

3. CONCLUSION

As expected, due to lower sampling activities, fewer samples have been collected during the current reporting period compared to the previous. Still, with more than 1,300 individuals sampled and more than 2,300 samples collected from over 30 species in eight countries, the coverage of active surveillance of avian influenza viruses in wild birds in and near Europe remains high.

At the wider European scale, surveillance data continue to indicate high levels of avian influenza virus circulation in wild birds, particularly in central Europe, and the overall situation remains critical. In the SENTINEL Wild Birds active surveillance, however, the overall bird-level prevalence has decreased from 10% in the January report to 3% in the current period, and only a single new HPAI detection was made. This decline is consistent with a seasonal transition from the intense transmission associated with autumn migration, dominated by large-scale bird movements and high proportions of immunologically naïve juveniles, to a winter situation with more stable local distributions and accumulated immunity in surviving birds.

At the species level, no particular host stands out as a major driver of virus circulation during this reporting period. Among species sampled in sufficient numbers (≥ 50 individuals), the highest bird-level prevalence was observed in Greylag Goose and Mallard (both 4%), followed by Black-headed Gull and Eurasian Wigeon (3%) and Eurasian Teal (2%). These values are only marginally higher than the overall prevalence of 3%, and apparent higher prevalence estimates in species with very small sample sizes (e.g. Gadwall and Common Pochard) should be interpreted with caution. Taken together, the current data suggest relatively homogeneous low-level circulation across the main sampled species.

Two samples from hunted Mallards in Latvia, previously reported as positive for AIV, have now been confirmed as HPAI virus-positive by rRT-PCR. The samples were collected in late October 2025 (H5N1; first-year female) and early November 2025 (H5N2; adult male). The latter represents the first confirmed highly pathogenic H5N2 virus detected within the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Although H5N1 remains the dominant HPAI subtype in Europe, the detection of an H5N2 HPAI virus in a wild Mallard underlines the genetic diversity within the H5 2.3.4.4b lineage that circulates in wild waterfowl during a season.

During this period, 20 H5 sequences have been generated, all of which were from the 2.3.4.4b HPAI clade. Where it was possible to determine the genotype of these H5 HPAI sequences, all were of the DI.2.1 sub-genotype, which has predominated in Europe since mid-September 2025 (EFSA *et al.* 2025), and they demonstrate high similarity to sequences collected across Europe, including other sequences generated by the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. In line with previous reports, this genetic similarity highlights the connectivity between the active sampling performed within SENTINEL Wild Birds and other passive surveillance schemes across the region.

In addition to the H5 sequences, several other subtypes were also detected, including H6, H9, and H12. These findings are consistent with previous SENTINEL Wild Birds reports and further support the picture of high subtypic diversity of avian influenza viruses circulating in wild birds.

Overall, the current reporting period documents a transition from widespread transmission during autumn migration to more localised, lower-level circulation during the mid-winter period. The clear decrease in prevalence and number of newly detected HPAI infections should therefore be viewed as a seasonal shift rather than an indication that the risk has passed. Continued coordinated surveillance, together with timely genomic analysis, will remain essential for tracking the evolution and spread of HPAI viruses and for providing early warning of future changes in virus dynamics in wild birds across Europe.

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Node 1: LABRIS, Riigi Laboriuuringute ja Riskihindamise Keskus (Estonia); Ruokavirasto, Finnish Food Authority (Finland); University of Turku (Finland)

Node 2: Swedish National Veterinary Institute (SVA) (Sweden); Linnaeus University (Sweden); Institute of Food Safety, Animal Health and Environment "BIOR" (Latvia); National Food and Veterinary Risk Assessment Institute (Lithuania); State Food and Veterinary Service (Lithuania); National Veterinary Research Institute (Poland)

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